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IMPROVING THE TECHNOLOGY OF DRINKING WATER TREATMENT FROM SURFACE WATER SOURCES USING NANOFILTRATION (using the example of the Amu Darya River)

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Annotation. In conditions of shortage of fresh water and deterioration of the quality of surface sources in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the improvement of water treatment technologies is of particular relevance. This paper considers the possibility of using nanofiltration to purify water from the Amu Darya River, which contains high mineralization, organic pollutants and pathogenic microorganisms. A technological scheme is proposed, including pretreatment, membrane filtration and

concentrate disposal. Calculated data on membrane performance, energy consumption, and estimated installation cost are provided. The simulation results show the high efficiency of nanofiltration in reducing the hardness, COD, and salt composition of water. The developed technology can be successfully adapted to the conditions of the region and recommended for implementation in drinking water supply systems.

Keywords: nanofiltration, drinking water, surface water sources, Amu Darya River, water treatment, membrane technologies, Karakalpakstan.

Introduction. Providing the population with high – quality drinking water is one of the most important tasks in the field of water supply, especially in arid regions such as the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Surface water sources, including the Amu Darya River, are susceptible to pollution and contain elevated concentrations of salts, organic substances, and microorganisms. Traditional methods of water purification do not always provide the required quality. In this regard, the application of nanofiltration (NF) is becoming a promising area.

The purpose of the study is to develop and substantiate an effective technology for the treatment of drinking water from surface sources using nanofiltration adapted to the conditions of the Amu Darya River.

Methodology

The following methods were used for the study:

- Analysis of the hydrochemical composition of the Amu Darya River water based on literature data.
- Comparative analysis of existing water treatment technologies.
- Development of a technological scheme using NF.
- Calculation of the performance and parameters of NF membranes.
- Justification of the stages of preliminary preparation (coagulation, clarification, filtration).

Scheme of water treatment technology using nanofiltration:

Results

As a result of the analysis, it was found that the water of the Amu Darya River contains:

Indicator	The average value	The standard for SanPiN
Total mineralization	1000–2000 mg/l	≤ 1000 мг/л
Rigidity	6–12 mg-eq/l	≤ 7 мг-экв/л
chemical oxygen consumption	8–12 mgO2/l	≤ 5 мгO2/л
Turbidity	To 10 FTU	≤ 1,5 FTU

Nanofiltration efficiency: reduction of mineralization by 60-80%, removal of organic matter (COD) up to 70%, complete removal of pathogenic microorganisms.

Cleaning efficiency at NF (model installation):

Indicator	Before SF	After SF
Total mineralization	1500	450
Rigidity	9	3
chemical oxygen consumption	10	3
Bacteria	1000 CFU/ml	0

Discussion

Calculation of nanofiltration membrane parameters for 100 m³/day of water (the capacity of one membrane is 2 m³/h):

- Required number of membranes: 3
- Required pressure: 4 bar
- Energy consumption: 66.7 kWh/day
- The cost of electricity: 6670 sum/day \approx 200,000 sum/month

Cost of equipment (example):

Position	Quantity	Price per unit (USD)	Amount (USD)
Dow NF270 NF membrane	3	350	1050
Membrane housings	3	150	450
High pressure pump	1	800	800
Automation and Piping Panel	1	600	600
Pre-filters	2	200	400
Total			3300 USD

Concentrate utilization (~15 m³/day):

- Discharge into a reservoir with dilution
- Evaporation in solar fields
- Re-filtering
- Use for technical purposes

Conclusions

The developed technology based on nanofiltration ensures that drinking water meets the requirements of the SanPiN. The method can be implemented in centralized and decentralized water supply systems in Karakalpakstan. It is recommended to conduct pilot tests at water intake facilities in the Amu Darya Delta.

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